

IMPROVING THE SYSTEM OF EXERCISES THAT DEVELOP THE THINKING OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN AND PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Annotation: This article reflects on the use of methods, types of methods, motivations for logical thinking to improve the system of exercises that develop divergent thinking of preschool children and primary school students.

Keywords: divergent thinking, logical thinking, attention, thinking, method, types of method, interactive, intellectual

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada maktabgacha bo'lgan bolalar va boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining divergent tafakkurini rivojlantiruvchi mashqlar tizimini takomillashtirish uchun metodlardan foydalanish, metod turlari, mantiqiy fikrlashga undash haqida fikr yuritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: turlicha fikrlash, mantiqiy fikrlash, e'tibor, fikrlash, metod, metod turlari, interaktiv, intellektual

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается использование методов совершенствования системы упражнений, развивающих дивергентное мышление учащихся младших классов, виды методов, мотивация к логическому мышлению.

Ключевые слова: дивергентное мышление, логическое мышление, внимание, мышление, метод, типы методов, интерактивное, интеллектуальное.

Introduction: The economic, cultural, social, scientific and technological progress of the Republic of Uzbekistan largely depends on the activities of the owners of intelligence, creative, creative activity, as well as their extensive knowledge. The incomparable role of education in the development of all spheres in our society has been taken into account, efforts are continuing at an accelerated pace towards the goal of improving the content of the educational system, harmonizing it with the requirements of the period. Today, educating the mentally mature, morally pure, physically strong, spiritually rich generation in society is one of the most important and urgent tasks for our independent state. Based on the abilities and high capabilities of Primary School students, the research work devoted to the organization of their education at the appropriate level is a minority, which indicates that this problem is very poorly studied psychologically. In the educational process, students increase their knowledge funds by acquiring a system of knowledge, learning skills and qualifications, so at the same time the fundamental meaning of

scientific concepts goes into their minds. In order to carry out all this work sequentially, evenly, the reader must have acquired a certain level of knowledge and skills, and, moreover, have mastered the forms of thinking and the rules of logical reasoning.

It follows from this that on the basis of the development of intellectual opportunities, the primary class emphasizes the absence of a single point of view on the organization of students' education and its content provision. At this point, it is appropriate to mention the meaning of the word intellectual. The lexical meaning of the word intellectual –means mental maturity, comprehension, intelligence, ingenuity, ingenuity, that is, a person with intelligence, ingenuity, creating the technology of self-development of a student at the moment is one of the pressing problems waiting for a solution before the science of pedagogy, didactics. What is personality-focused education among teachers in later times? Why is training in interactive method necessary? What are its types? What is the structural structure? How to bring it into the educational process? What is its difference from previous methods? questions are encountered. To find the exact answers to these questions, one more time to analyze the traditional lessons conducted in our secondary schools. An the traditional method was proposed in the 17th century by the Czech pedagogical scientist Yan Amos Komensky.

He develops a unified classical system of teaching, which he maintains as a class –lesson system. Later, this system became widespread in pedagogy. The traditional school class lesson system has its own traditions as follows: approximately the same or near-year-old, with the level of preparation close by children make up the class. The class works on the basis of a single plan, program, textbook, lesson schedule. The type of training is basically the only lesson. The lesson works on a specific subject of study, the same material on the topic. The students' activities are managed by the teacher, assessing the level of knowledge of each student, moving the student from class to class at the end of the he decides, that is, the decision of the fate of the students is in the hands of the teacher. Now let's dwell on interactive methods in more detail. Interactive methods are such methods that it is a method that carries out the course process in the interaction and interaction of students. Classification of interactive education methods.. From the above, it becomes known the need to duly analyze interactive educational methods and, on this basis, classify them. Below we will provide general feedback on this issue. When classifying these techniques, they can be divided into interactive methods, interactive educational strategies, interactive graphic organizers. Currently, the most popular interactive educational methods are listed as follows: 1. Interactive methods: -Keys-stadi (or-training keys) -Blist-query, -Modeling, -creative work, -problem education and b.2. Interactive education strategies.-Mental attack, Boomerang, Zig-zag, Zinama -zina, Muzorar, Rotatsiya, -

rounded snow and k. The approach to the organization of group work in the separation of interactive educational strategies from the content of interactive educational methods is based, in a certain sense, on the comparison of the strategy. In fact, these strategies also belong more to interactive educational methods, among which there are no other differences.3. Interactive graphic organizers: -fish skeleton, -BBB, -conceptual table-Venn diagram,-t table, -Insert, -cluster, -why?,-How? and b. When distinguishing interactive graphic organizers, the main points in such training are based on the fact that they are expressed in writing in different graphic forms. In fact, working with these graphic organizers is also more concerned with interactive educational methods, among which there are no other differences. Interactive educational methods are often used at the same time as training technologies in different forms. The use of these techniques serves to improve the effectiveness of education by increasing the activity of the participants in the training.

In conclusion, it can be said that one of the requirements of the current period is the upbringing of creative young people who can think logically. The service of primary school teachers in the education of such young people is great in benihoya. Especially the elementary school teacher should teach students creativity in classes.To improve the effectiveness of training and to mature children, the content of the issue that is given the most before will be given the most effective benefit if first of all attention is paid to it

References:

1. Xodjayev B.X. Umumiy pedagogika nazariyasi va amaliyoti. Darslik–T. Sano-Standart, 2017.
2. XodjayevB.X., ChoriyevA., SaliyevaZ.T. Pedagogik tadqiqotlar metodologiyasi. Darslik T. Iqtisodiyot Dunyosi,2018.
3. Begimkulov U.SH. Pedagogik ta’lim jarayonlarini axborotlashtirishni tashkil etish va boshqarish nazariyasi va amaliyoti. //Ped. fanlari dokt. ilmiy dar. uchun diss. -T.: 2007,
4. Djumayeva S. Ijtimoiy va pedagogik nizolar: mohiyati va bartaraf etish yo‘llari. //Metodik qo‘llanma. -T.: Nizomiy nomidagi TDPU, 2011.